

Problems Encountered by Filipino Teachers in the Delivery of Blended Learning Modality

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Abstract:

In contrast to blended learning in the Philippines, which combines online and printed self-learning modules, blended or hybrid learning in Indonesia combines remote learning via online and in-person instruction. According to Perdani et al. (2021), the blended learning approach involves splitting students into two groups. The first group learns online by working virtually from home, while the second group participates in offline learning by interacting with their lecturers in person in the classroom. This study aimed to determine the degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the delivery of Blended Learning Modality, in a Coastal City in Central Java, Indonesia for the School Year 2021-2022 as basis for an intervention plan. This descriptive quantitative study made use of 45 respondents and covered the areas of learning resources, assessments and parental support. The result of the study showed that in all of the aforesaid areas, the problems encountered by teachers were all manageable at "low level". Furthermore, there was no significant difference in the degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The study highlighted several recommendations that focused on learning strategies instead of resources, assessment techniques and parental support.

Keywords: Blended learning, Filipino teachers, problems encountered, intervention plan

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Over 68 million students, ranging from preschoolers to college students, were impacted by Indonesia's school closures in the 2020-2021 academic year. In order to establish a secure and effective learning environment during the pandemic, blended learning—which combines online and in-person instruction—was offered as a solution to the difficulties in fully utilizing online classes (Muna and Krismantari, 2020).

In contrast to blended learning in the Philippines, which combines online and printed self-learning modules, blended or hybrid learning in Indonesia combines remote learning via online and in-person instruction. According to Perdani et al. (2021), the blended learning approach involves splitting students into two groups. The first group learns online by working virtually from home, while the second group participates in offline learning by interacting with their lecturers in person in the classroom.

Lack of learning resources, inadequate teacher training in integrating technology into blended learning, inadequate internet connection, and student-parent preparedness are some of the difficulties faced by educators and learners in blended learning, according to The Conversation Indonesia (2020).

As a Filipino educator employed in Indonesia, the researcher faces challenges adjusting to the localized blended learning educational system. Many of them have found that switching classes has been difficult because, in addition to managing online courses, they still need to attend class at least twice a week. Despite the irregular internet connection, Filipino teachers must contend with web-based courses, live videos, and conference calls throughout the era of this preferred learning technique. Additionally, Filipino professors must report to class in person despite experiencing serious health problems as a result of the pandemic. The researcher was inspired to carry out this investigation by these insights and encounters.

Current State of Knowledge

In the final decades of the 20th century, distance learning approaches began gaining traction as advancements in communication technologies and the growing need for lifelong learning reshaped educational practices. Today, these methods are central to modern education, yet many project leaders lack a deep understanding of distance education's full potential. Often, financial incentives overshadow academic considerations, with computer companies profiting while higher education leaders focus on cost-efficiency rather than learning outcomes (Garrison, 2020). This shift has laid the groundwork for more technology-integrated models like blended and online learning, despite ongoing implementation challenges.

Blended learning, which combines online and face-to-face instruction, promises greater flexibility and efficiency for both teachers and students. For instance, as Perdani et al. (2021) note, hybrid learning allows classroom time to be more adaptable to individual student needs and schedules, and features such as recorded lessons add convenience. However, despite its advantages, blended learning presents real obstacles—particularly in resource-constrained environments. As Schissel (2020) points out, the high cost of devices such as laptops and tablets makes it difficult for many students and teachers to fully participate, especially in schools with limited budgets.

These financial and logistical barriers are evident in the Philippines, where blended learning remains in its infancy. According to the Manila Bulletin (2021), schools face widespread issues such as inadequate training, technical problems, and content adaptation difficulties. More importantly, blended learning has strained relationships between students and teachers while diminishing learner motivation. In a study by Alvarez (2020), facilitators of the National Service Training Program (NSTP) reported challenges related to teamwork, class size, and insufficient technical support. These findings highlight the urgent need for sustained teacher development and improved infrastructure in higher education.

On the ground level, similar issues persist in modular distance learning, particularly in rural areas. Baculad, Dejito, and Bautista (2025) examined the experiences of 38 teachers in San Jose District, Negros Oriental, and found moderate difficulties in planning, preparation, module distribution and retrieval, and student assessment. While demographic factors had little impact, educational attainment did influence how teachers managed these tasks. Key challenges included late module returns, poor parental support, and reliance on unfamiliar pre-made materials. The study called for better scheduling, collaboration with local government, and enhanced teacher training to strengthen modular instruction.

These nationwide experiences echo the struggles seen in urban centers like Jakarta, where students switched to online learning for safety reasons during the pandemic. Angdhiri (2020) reported that students, unprepared for the abrupt shift, found home-based learning more stressful than traditional classes. The absence of in-person interaction and the isolation of working alone with constant assignments negatively affected student morale. As one student put it, "Normal classes may have been challenging, but having friends makes it so much more manageable."

Given these varying perspectives, it is clear that choosing between online, blended, or traditional teaching settings depends on personal, institutional, and situational factors. As Goodwin (2017) argues, while educators may prefer face-to-face teaching, they must recognize the growing importance of technology in education. Incorporating digital tools—regardless of the chosen model—not only supports student engagement but also prepares both learners and teachers for a more flexible, resilient educational future.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The Theory of Optimal Challenges by John Dodson and Robert Yerkes (1908) serves as the foundation for our investigation. This hypothesis was specifically created to describe the many difficulties that educators face. By accomplishing the following goals, the theory of sustained optimal challenge helps students learn: it continuously modifies the pace and content difficulty levels during instruction; it aligns the expectations of the teachers with the aptitudes (abilities and inabilities) of the students; and, lastly, it lessens the variance in student learning. In a variety of fields, such as statistics, mechanics, quality, and ergonomics, the central limit theorem, teaching and learning theories, learning outcomes, and student feedback all backed up the suggested hypothesis. The majority of courses that were taught using the suggested theory showed sustained optimal challenges. This theory is relevant to the current study because it takes into consideration the various difficulties that public elementary school teachers face when providing offline materials to meet the needs of students enrolled in distant learning programs in the new normal. Because it takes into consideration every aspect of the difficulties teachers face in maintaining students' highest levels of engagement and making sure that all other connected issues are appropriately handled, this theory is equally relevant to the study.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the delivery of Blended Learning Modality, in one of the city states of an Asian country for the School Year 2021-2022 as basis for an intervention plan. Furthermore, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) determine the

degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the areas of: Learning Resources, Assessment of Learning and Parental Support, and 2) determine if there is a significant difference in the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia, and average family monthly income.

Methodology:

Research Design

To ascertain the degree of difficulties faced by Filipino secondary school teachers in one of the Asian country's metropolis states when utilizing the blended learning modality, a descriptive approach was used. It is a design that describes one or more variables using both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. A population, circumstance, or phenomena can be accurately described by descriptive research, claims McCombes (2019). This study strategy works better when describing the characteristics of the variables is the aim.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 45 Filipino teachers in Cirebon City, West Java in Indonesia for the school year 2021–2022. The paper made use of purposive sampling to determine the sample size.

Research Instrument

To determine the extent of challenges encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the City of Cirebon in Indonesia in the utilization of Blended Learning Modality, this study made use of a self-made data-gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity (4.67 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.955 interpreted as "excellent"). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia, and average family monthly income. Part 2 contained the questionnaire proper with 30-line items. There were 10-line items per area, with a total of 3 different areas from instructional supervision and technical assistance skills.

Data Collection Procedure

After establishing the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher wrote a letter to the District Superintendent asking permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researcher allowed 5 days for the data gathering instrument to be returned to schools by the respondents. In the conduct of this study, the researcher explained the purpose of the study through a cover letter and the data gathering instruments administered through Google form, email or instant messaging to the respondents. This is to ensure that face-to-face interactions between the researcher and the respondents or among respondents themselves are reduced.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used descriptive analytical schemes and mean as statistical tools to determine the degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in terms of learning resources, assessment of learning and parental support.

Objective No. 2 used comparative analytical scheme to determine if there is a significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Ethical Consideration

This research paper strived in earnest to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and protecting their anonymity throughout the entire research process. At the onset, this researcher secured their free, prior informed consent and assured them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary.

Results and Discussions:

This section presents the data, the analysis, and the interpretation of the same to meet the study's objectives as stated in the objectives. All of these were made possible by adhering to specific protocols that provided precise data and solutions for every objective.

Degree of Problems Encountered by Filipino Secondary School Teachers in the area of Learning Resources, Assessment of Learning and Parental Support

Table 1

Degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the area of learning resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...		
1. sourcing for the right lesson contents for my students.	2.28	Low Degree
2. contextualizing each lesson so that learners can easily understand each lesson.	2.26	Low Degree
3. integrating ICT-based learning.	2.35	Low Degree
4. employing teaching strategies that is centered on literacy and numeracy.	2.40	Low Degree
5. utilizing strategic critical and creative thinking skills.	2.46	Low Degree
6. designing an effective communication strategy tailored on learners' needs	2.31	Low Degree
7. demonstrating the right understanding of lesson contents.	2.31	Low Degree
8. sharing a wider content-knowledge experience across curriculum areas.	2.42	Low Degree
9. collaborating efforts with co-teachers to improve my own pedagogical strategies.	2.15	Low Degree
10. preparing lessons based on learners identified most essential learning competencies (MELCs).	2.22	Low Degree
Mean	2.32	Low Degree

Table 1 reveals the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary teachers in Indonesia with a mean score of 2.32, interpreted as "low degree".

Item No. 9 which states that "As a teacher I am challenged in collaborating efforts with co-teachers to improve my own pedagogical strategies" got the lowest mean score of 2.15; while, Item No. 5 which states that "As a teacher I am challenged in utilizing strategic critical and creative thinking skills" got the highest mean score of 2.46, interpreted as "low degree".

This implies that secondary Filipino teachers in Indonesia were mostly challenged in exploring critical and creative thinking skills for students while in blended learning modality. Teaching students such skills may require project-based learning which is mostly done face-to-face. Although this line item is the highest mean, its low degree category means that this is somewhat manageable and teachers can get through it using other means.

In Indonesia, particularly in large cities like Jakarta, students continue their education through online courses and video conferences with their instructors. Since keeping schools open puts students' safety at danger, this strategy is now the greatest option. Since we hadn't been prepped with simulations or practices previously, it was difficult for us as students enrolled in the home-learning program to become used to online learning. Even more stressful than traditional classroom settings, according to students, was the home-learning program. "Normal classes may have been challenging, but having friends makes it so much more manageable and less stressful," was one of the frequently cited explanations for this. Online classes take out the benefits of having friends to socialize with and being stuck alone with nothing but assignments" (Angdhiri, 2020).

Table 2

Degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the area of assessment of learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...		
1. making sure that assessments are content-based.	2.28	Low Degree
2. creating MELC-based assessments.	2.31	Low Degree
3. using assessment results as guide for future lessons.	2.37	Low Degree
4. using assessment results as basis for individual coaching.	2.40	Low Degree
5. conducting regular confirmation of learning through exams.	2.51	Moderate Degree
6. utilizing standardized assessment format.	2.24	Low Degree
7. there is no regular assessment schedule.	2.13	Low Degree
8. reaching assessment targets.	2.42	Low Degree
9. ensuring that learners are able to catch up with lesson contents prior to assessments.	2.13	Low Degree
10. providing a peer-reviewed/validated exam.	2.02	Low Degree
Mean	2.28	Low Degree

Table 2 shows the overall mean score of 2.28 which interpreted as "low degree". Item No. 10 which states "As a teacher, I am challenged in providing a peer-reviewed/ validated exam" got the lowest mean score of 2.02 interpreted as low degree; while Item No. 5 which states "As a teacher, I am challenged in conducting regular confirmation of learning through exams" got the highest mean score of 2.51, interpreted as moderate degree.

Confirmation of learning, done through various assessment methods can be real when they are given in school, while the teacher is supervising the exam without parents around. In cases where exams are provided online or via self-learning modules, the competence of the result is mostly tainted because the students are tempted to seek the help of their parents and siblings. This scenario may put teachers in a precarious situation.

It can be difficult to decide which teaching setting is best for you because both online and offline provide a variety of advantages and difficulties. To determine which path is ideal for them, educators should take into account the information in this blog post as well as their personal, professional, and personal preferences. Regardless of how teachers feel about it, technology will continue to become an increasingly important teaching tool, so even if they prefer to work in a traditional classroom setting, it is still worthwhile to think about incorporating more technology to improve the learning process (Goodwin, 2017).

Table 3

Degree of problems encountered by Filipino Secondary School teachers in the area of parental support

Items As a teacher, I am challenged in ...	Mean	Interpretation
1. getting parents commitment to facilitate learners' education at home.	2.20	Low Degree
2. making sure that parents are on time to receive/return the modules.	2.31	Low Degree
3. keeping parents' compliance to social distancing and health protocols in school.	2.42	Low Degree
4. asking parents to guide learners' online education.	2.28	Low Degree
5. receiving parents participating in accomplishing learners' projects.	2.22	Low Degree
6. letting parents assist their children with emotional issues.	2.31	Low Degree
7. assisting their children's performance tasks and outputs.	2.11	Low Degree
8. getting the cooperation of the parents in implementing study hours at home.	2.15	Low Degree
9. asking parents to put a balance between study time and play time for the children at home.	2.22	Low Degree
10. establishing a consistent connection with the parents.	2.22	Low Degree
Mean	2.24	Low Degree

Table 3 shows the overall mean score of 2.24 which interpreted as low degree. Item No. 7 which states that "As a teacher, I am challenged in assisting children's performance tasks and outputs" got the lowest mean score of 2.11; while, Item No. 3 which states that "As a teacher, I am challenged in keeping parents' compliance to social distancing and health protocols in school" got the highest mean score of 2.42; both line items are interpreted as "low degree".

The problem faced by teachers with poor or minimal compliance in social distancing and other health protocol among students in school is a reflection of how parents educate their children at home. While the mean score for this line item showed as low degree, being the highest, means that parental involvement in this specific case is somewhat lacking.

According to the responses, there are four main reasons why blended learning is difficult to implement: 1) insufficient tools made especially for adult learners, 2) a lack of practitioner expertise, 3) practical difficulties with Wi-Fi and tool access, and 4) opposition. Many of the issues raised imply that in order to help teachers overcome them, they require significant professional development. Additionally, they clarify that blended learning is not a panacea. Access problems in rural and underprivileged populations limit its potential. It may be impractical to expect students to devote a significant amount of time to extracurricular learning activities. Decisions for blended learning instructional design should take into account the realities of adult lives and responsibilities (Schissel, 2020).

Comparative Analysis in the Degree of Problems Encountered by Filipino Secondary School Teachers in the area of Learning Resources, Assessment of Learning and Parental Support when grouped and compared according to Age, Sex, Civil Status, Number of Years in Indonesia and Average Family Monthly Income

Table 4

Difference in the Degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the Area of learning resources When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	17	21.29	209.000	0.492	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	28	24.04				
Sex	Male	14	25.86	177.000	0.321	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	31	21.71				
Civil Status	Single	20	24.28	224.500	0.156	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	25	21.98				
Number of Years in Indonesia	Shorter	18	20.17	192.000	0.232	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	24.89				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	22	21.05	210.000	0.324	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	23	24.87				

Table 4 shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia and average family monthly income obtained the Mann-Whitney U test and p -value which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as not significant. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the area of learning resources when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables" was hereby accepted.

The result in this table reveals the fact that all respondents - regardless of their age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia or their average family monthly income the teachers commonly share the same degree of problems in terms of learning resources. Since there is a prior knowledge that the degree of problems is low, this means that the problems encountered by teachers in the learning resources is simply uniformly manageable.

Distance education methodologies have come into prominence during the last decades of the 20th century. The confluence of the need for continuous learning and unprecedented technological innovation in communications have pushed distance education approaches to the forefront of educational practice. However, whether the leaders of these initiatives are the technically literate or the politically powerful, they generally lack a coherent understanding of distance education practice and the full range of possibilities available to achieve desired outcomes. Senior administrators in higher education have become focused, not on educational issues, but the fiscal implications (i.e., cost savings) of distance education, and technology companies see profits (Garrison, 2020).

Table 5

Difference in the Degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the Area of assessment of learning When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	17	19.68	181.500	0.178	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	28	25.02				
Sex	Male	14	28.00	147.000	0.081	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	31	20.74				
Civil Status	Single	20	20.08	191.500	0.174	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	25	25.34				
Number of Years in Indonesia	Shorter	18	24.78	211.000	0.451	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	21.81				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	22	24.77	214.000	0.368	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	23	21.30				

Table 5 shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia and average family monthly income obtained the Mann-Whitney U test and *p*-value which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as not significant. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the area of assessment of learning when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables" was hereby accepted.

The result implies that in terms of assessment, the teachers have shared experiences in terms of assess and the degree of problems is indeed just manageable being on low level.

These days, e-learning is becoming more and more popular, and blended learning is one way to put this idea into practice. The successful fusion of various delivery methods, instructional models, and learning styles that are practiced in an engaging, interactive learning environment is known as blended learning.

In order to improve student learning outcomes and address significant institutional concerns, blended learning courses integrate online and classroom learning activities and make best use of available resources. The natural blending of carefully chosen and complimentary in-person and virtual learning methods and tools is known as blended learning. Generally speaking, blended learning blends the best aspects of live instruction and classroom interaction with online delivery of educational content to allow for thoughtful reflection, differentiate instruction from student to student across a diverse group of learners, and personalize learning (Watson). Definitions of blended learning from various perspectives (Kaur, 2015).

Table 6

Difference in the Degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the Area of parental support When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	17	22.53	230.000	0.849		Not Significant
	Older	28	23.29				
Sex	Male	14	23.11	215.500	0.970	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	31	22.95				
Civil Status	Single	20	22.20	234.000	0.710		Not Significant
	Married	25	23.64				
Number of Years in Indonesia	Shorter	18	23.78	229.000	0.742	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	27	22.48				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	22	21.05	210.000	0.231	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	23	24.87				

Table 6 shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, number of years in Indonesia and average family monthly income obtained the Mann-Whitney U test and *p*-value which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as not significant. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of problems encountered by Filipino secondary school teachers in the area of parental support when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables" was hereby accepted.

This implies that the teachers have the same common concern regarding parental support. Across all respondents, there degree of problems encountered by teachers is indeed manageable.

At first glance, blended learning sounds like a dream for students and teachers. Theoretically, class time is reduced, and the process of instruction is streamlined through the use of technology. Who wouldn't want that? However, blended learning presents unique challenges that can become barriers to learning. Let's take a closer look at some of these challenges now. Technology is Expensive. Many traditional classrooms have a computer present for student and teacher use. Some traditional classrooms have even more than one computer, depending on school budgets. Blended learning usually requires that all students and teachers have a computer, tablet, or laptop. Needless to say, this is expensive to implement and maintain (Schissel, 2020).

Conclusion:

The study found that the majority of respondents were older, mostly female, married, and had longer tenures as educators in Indonesia, with income levels nearly equally divided. Filipino Secondary School teachers reported low degrees of problems in blended learning, specifically in learning resources, assessments, and parental support—indicating these issues were manageable and did not significantly disrupt school operations. No significant differences in challenges were found across variables such as age, gender, marital status, or teaching experience, suggesting that teachers across all demographics experienced and managed similar issues effectively. To support and enhance teaching practices, the study recommends three programs: CACTA, to foster critical and creative thinking among students through guided activities; RAP, to improve assessment methods via reflective, narrative-based evaluations; and a school-parent agreement to ensure parental adherence to school safety protocols.

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